

From Margins to Mainstream: Women Empowerment in Gram Panchayats of Haryana Challenges, Strategies, and Success Stories

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ABSTRACT

The most meaningful benchmark of a nation's democratic health is the extent of equal, actual, and effective women's role in the electoral process. Women's inclusion in political structures is necessary for advancing their interests and for reinforcing legitimacy of the democracy (Rai, 2017). However, the patriarchal value system in many societies, including India, has systematically excluded women from political spheres, which led to their subjugation and dependence on men. Therefore, to promote women's interests and empower them politically, "more than 130 countries" globally have adopted gender-based quotas at both "national and local levels" (Hughes et al. 2019). India did the same in 1992 with the "73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendment Acts", and Haryana provided gender reservations through its Panchayati Raj Act 1994 and subsequent amendments. The affirmative action policy has been instrumental in the political empowerment of women in Haryana allowing them to display their leadership skills. However, on the other hand, women in Haryana are still denied the right to actively participate in local governance due to social and institutional constraints. Though their numerical strength has been increasing in local politics, in reality, they still do not exercise real power and influence on decision-making in local institutions. Therefore, this gap makes it pertinent to analyse the impact of gender-based reservation at grassroots levels on women in Haryana and to identify the impediments still being faced by them in making the best use of gender quotas available for their empowerment.

Keywords: Women Empowerment, Gender Quotas, Patriarchy, 73rd and 74th Amendment Acts, Haryana Panchayati Raj Act 1994

INTRODUCTION

In most of the countries, women are still denied basic social, economic, and political rights. India is not an exception. Indian women have been denied an independent role in decision making and the culprit has been a deeply entrenched patriarchal value system deeply entrenched in Indian social life. Even though regional variations

do exist in terms of the impact of patriarchal values in the sense that north India is more notorious for being more patriarchal south India is not completely free from its influence. The dictates of the male members of their families have been guiding decisions taken by women in India (Mohanty, 2005). Therefore,

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patriarchy is a social system where cultural and social norms give preference to men and put restrictions on opportunities for women vesting all social, economic, and political power vested in men (Aggarwal, 2016).

However, social justice, democracy, and human development call for an egalitarian society based on gender equality. This calls for a greater engagement of women in politics and their representation in other decision-making bodies. Women's involvement in political decision-making is significant from both normative and practical aspects. Normatively, it would ensure the representation of almost 50% of the population in the decision-making process and practically it would ensure that policies and decisions are not made from the male perspective only and would also take care of the interests of women (Khanna, 2009). The pathetic position of women caused many progressive men and women to launch movements aimed at women's empowerment and establishing an egalitarian social order in many countries like India. Women in India have come a long way as far as political leadership and decision making is concerned. The moment towards political empowerment of Indian women started with their participation in India's freedom struggle and then in numerous social moments after independence (Misra, 2010). One of the most critical decisions for empowering women was the passage of the "73rd and 74th Amendment Acts" which provided gender reservation in institutions of local self-governance. Haryana also provided gender quotas through its Panchayati Raj Act 1994 and subsequent amendments. Even though a lot has been done to

empower women socially, economically, and politically, their status as compared to men remains inferior globally (Ghosh et al. 2015). This is also true for India. India has adopted development planning and incorporated special provisions for women in the Constitution but still, a considerable number of women, especially, rural women are yet to be empowered (Fadia, 2014). They still suffer from political discrimination which has further debilitated their already feeble position in society. Haryana also suffers from the same problem of gender discrimination. Thus, while recognizing and supporting women's involvement in electoral politics and decision-making especially at grassroots levels, this paper intends to manifest the ground reality of women's empowerment in Haryana in respect of their participation in Gram Panchayats.

METHODOLOGY

This paper is an endeavour to understand the working and impact of gender quotas in Haryana. The paper is based on secondary data that will be collected from various news articles, journals, field studies, different websites, and reports by various organizations and governments.

OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the empowering outcomes of gender quotas in Gram Panchayats on women in Haryana.
2. To study the constraints and the reasons for these constraints being faced by women in availing the benefits of gender-based reservation in Gram Panchayats in Haryana.
3. To propose feasible suggestions for ensuring genuine empowerment of women.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The concept of empowerment and women empowerment

Empowerment - Concept and Meaning

The meaning of the term according to most dictionaries is “to empower”, and ‘to give power to’. In a simple sense, it means gradual transfer of power in a dynamic way. As per the World Bank (2005), “empowerment is the process of enhancing the capacity of individuals or groups to make choices and to transform those choices into desired actions and outcomes”. Similarly, as per Kabeer (2001), “empowerment involves enlarged participation in decision-making, and through participation in decision-making, people start feeling that they have the right and capability to make decisions”. According to Fadia (2014), empowerment means “decentralisation of authority and power”. According to “the Government of India Country Report, Empowerment means moving from a position of enforced powerlessness to one of power” (Venkatesh & Kala, 2010). Therefore, the people who are empowered, are free to make choices and are able to act as per their choices to achieve the desired results. The term empowerment has two important aspects. Firstly, empowerment means having the power to attain desired goals and does not mean the exercise of “power over others”. Secondly, the concept of empowerment applies primarily to those who lack power. These powerless may be “male/female/group/class/caste” (Sen and Batliwala, 2000).

Empowerment of Women - Concept and Meaning

Democracy becomes meaningful and

fruitful if it is participatory, which means, unhindered involvement of women in the community decision-making process. If it does not happen, the development is bound to be lopsided and partial. Therefore, it is quintessential that women are socially, economically, and politically empowered.

The need to empower is paramount to remove gender disparity which is a normal feature of many developing countries. Hence, rooting out gender disparity and promoting women’s empowerment have been incorporated by the United Nations as significant aspects of the Sustainable Development Goals (Kumar & Yadav, 2024). Women empowerment is a dynamic and complex notion and different definitions have been given in a variety of ways by theorists. As per Keller and Mbwewe (1991), women empowerment is “a process whereby women become able to organize themselves to increase their own self-reliance, to assert their independent right to make choices and to control resources which will assist in challenging and eliminating their own subordination” (Tandon, 2016). Women are empowered when they gain capabilities to regulate and direct their lives and destinies. A majority of definitions of women’s empowerment put emphasis on expanding “the choices and freedom” for women enabling them to decide and act in ways that shape their life outcomes (Malhotra and Schuler, 2005). Therefore, the concept is a change-oriented process wherein women get all capabilities and opportunities to make life choices within the same social environment in which these were denied to them earlier. The core of this viewpoint is enabling women to use resources

independently, as per their wisdom, needs, and requirements so that they can achieve their desired goals (Huis et.al, 2017). The concept of empowerment is not restricted to women only. It applies to all “individuals, classes, castes, families, and households” (Malhotra et al, 2002). Women’s empowerment rectifies the historic imbalance in power-sharing between men and women which restricted the attainment of human development. It has many dimensions: social, economic, political, cultural, psychological, cultural, and demographic, and each aspect is logically and coherently linked with each other. Therefore, empowerment requires improvement in all aspects which further requires many fundamental changes in social structures including within households recognizing that like men women are also capable and responsible for handling themselves, their families, their communities, and society (Chaudhary, et al., 2012). Therefore, when women gain greater power and control over their lives and life situations, we can say that women’s empowerment has set in.

WOMEN EMPOWERMENT AND GENDER QUOTA IN HARYANA

The state of Haryana is situated in north-west India and it came into being on 1st November 1966 when it was carved out of the former state of east Punjab based on language. Geographically, the state of Himachal Pradesh lies on its north, Uttar Pradesh forms its eastern boundary, Rajasthan lies to its south, and Punjab to its west. The total area of the state is

44212 sq.km. As per census 2011, “Haryana’s total population is 25351462, out of which 13494734 are males and 11856728 are females, the majority population is Hindu (87.46%) followed by Muslims (7.03%) and Sikhs (4.91%), which are in the minority” (Sangita & Sharma, 2024).

Why Haryana?

Haryana is an agrarian state and is notorious for its patriarchal, caste-based, and feudalistic social structures and gender-based discrimination and inequality. Due to social and cultural barriers, despite being one of the richest states of India, women in Haryana are still shrouded in *Ghunghat*. Traditional sayings like “TRIYA MAT PER JO CHALLE VOH HAIN NIRGYAN (those who follow a woman’s advice are fools)” in Haryana manifest the mindset of the people towards women. Despite tremendous political and economic development, Haryana is socially backward, in terms of various social indicators. Many Indian states, which are not as economically prosperous as Haryana, have managed to maintain higher levels of social indicators than Haryana (Participatory Research In Asia, 1998).

Women have been subjected to various kinds of discrimination and social exclusions. They are excluded from political decision-making (Sangita & Sharma, 2024). Since its inception, Haryana could elect 87 women to its state assembly, and in five state elections since 2000, Haryana could make only 47 women legislatures (Press Trust of India, 2024)

Table 1- Findings on social backwardness in Haryana

Sr. No	Indicator	Result	Observation
1.	Child Sex Ratio	80 points decline from 1961 to 2011(830)Lowest Child Sex ratio in India (914)	Son preference Female infanticideFemale foeticide Sex selective abortions
2.	Sex Ratio	Declined from 867 in 1901 to 819 in 2001. Though rose to 877 in 2011, it is still the lowest in country	Historically unfavourable trend in sex ratioManifests gender discrimination
3.	Literacy Rate	Overall: 76.6%Male: 84%Female: 65.9%Gender gap: 18.11%	Through literacy rate has been improvingGender gap in literacy rate still persists
4.	Women work force participation	Fell from 27.2% (2001) to 17.8% (2011) Is below national average.	Women are largely in unpaid rural labourA few of them are employerWage gap at 17.8% (2009-10).
5.	Crime against women	3.6% of total crimes committed against women in India happens in Haryana	Represent low status of women and patriarchy in Haryana

Source: Kanika, 2024

Table 2 - Other indicators showing gender-bias in Haryana

Indicator	Haryana	All India	Year
Female Labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR) all ages (ps+ss)	15.9%	27.8%	2022-23
Female Worker Population Ratio (WPR) all ages (ps+ss)	15.2%	27.0%	2022-23
Female Unemployment Rate (UR) average (ps+ss)	4.7%	2.9%	2022-23
Women MPs in Lok Sabha	10% (1 out of 10)	13.6% (74 out of 543)	2024
Women MLAs in State Assembly	10% (9 out of 90)	9% (average across states)	2019- 2023

These indicators reflect upon the social backwardness and gender bias that exists in Haryana. These poor social indicators have a profound impact on women. Gender-based inequality is deeply rooted in rural Haryana. Women in rural Haryana are less autonomous in decision-making, are more reliant on their families, and have restricted access to resources and, hence, often face difficulties in using them as per their preferences (Kumar & Yadav, 2024). The Government of Haryana has enacted its own Panchayati Raj Act, which contains provisions for reserving seats for women in local government institutions. Many women in Haryana have availed this opportunity and have been elected as *sarpanch/panch* of Gram Panchayats. However, the majority of them have faced and are still facing numerous hurdles, before getting elected and even after having been elected. This study endeavours to highlight the empowering impact of gender-based quotas on women as elected *sarpanch/panch* of Gram Panchayats in Haryana, the challenges being faced by them, and the reasons behind these challenges.

Panchayati Raj in Haryana

As a part of the state of Punjab after independence, the Punjab Gram Panchayat Act 1952 was implemented under which Gram Panchayats were established at the village level. At the time of the birth of Haryana in 1966 as a separate state, there was three tier structure of local government in operation in Haryana which included Gram Panchayats, Panchayat Samitis, and Zilla Parishads. Zilla Parishads were abrogated on “13th July 1973”. However, the three-

tier structure was restored by the Haryana Panchayati Raj Act 1994, which was implemented on 22nd April 1994 (Participatory Research In Asia, 1998). The 1994 act contained almost all the provisions of 73rd Amendment. “The Haryana Panchayati Raj Amendment Act 2015” was passed which laid down several conditions for contesting elections for PRIs. Some of these conditions include candidates requiring a mandatory functional toilet at home, general category male candidates to be 10th pass, women to be 8th pass, SC category women candidates have to be 5th pass, etc. (Shivani, 2019). The Act was again amended in 2020 which increased women’s reservation in PRIs from 33% to 50% (Ministry of Panchayati Raj).

Empowering impact of gender quota on women in Haryana

Gender quotas have given a platform for women to come out of their homes and take up public responsibilities. Without quotas, women would have never thought of even contesting Panchayat elections in Haryana. In Haryana, the strength of elected women *sarpanches* and *panches* has been increasing.

At present, there are 6,201 *sarpanches* in Haryana. Of them, 3,181 are men and 3,020 are women. Out of 3020 women *sarpanches*, 754 belong to the SC category and 397 to BC and OBC. There are 60039 total *panches* in Haryana. Of them, 31,828 are men and 28,211 are women. Out of 28211 women *panches*, 7911 belong to the SC category and 6138 to the BC and OBC categories (priharyana).

The gender quotas in Haryana have been instrumental in empowering women by way of their participation in Panchayats

in the state, by giving them political space, public visibility, and new identity/status. There have been instances where women *sarpanches* and *panches* have played significant developmental roles as local leaders. A study conducted on 295 women *sarpanches* in 21 districts in Haryana found despite many sociocultural problems, elected women representatives gained the capability to bring changes in governance in panchayats with time (Kumar & Ghosh,

2024). In six villages of the Jind district women representatives played significant roles in community development, leadership, and decision-making while facing myriad challenges. 71% of women *sarpanches* expressed a rise in confidence, 63% reported increased participation in local governance, and 58% reported this positive change in the community's perception (Dahiya & Thakur, 2025).

Table 3 - The rise in the strength of elected women representatives in Panchayats of Haryana over the years.

Year	Total Sarpanch	Total Women Sarpanch	Total Panch	Total Women Panch
1995	5958	1994 (33.5)	54169	17928 (33.0)
2000	6035	2009 (33.3)	54682	18037 (33.0)
2005	6187	2113 (34.2)	60401	22294 (36.9)
2010	6083	2022 (33.2)	58857	21766 (37.0)
2016	6186	2565 (41.5)	60436	25495 (42.2)
2022	6201	3017 (48.7)	58825	27614 (46.9)

Source: Duhan, 2018 & State Statistical Abstract of Haryana, 2023-24

Some success stories of women empowerment through gender quota in Haryana

Kamlesh Rani, as *sarpanch* of Rawanhera Village, district Kaithal played an active role in eradicating child marriages, and stood against Khap Panchayat's call to reduce the marriageable age for girls from "18 to 16 years". (Kumar, 2025).

Parveen Kaur of Kakrala Kuchiyan Village in Kaithal district. She was elected *sarpanch* in 2016 while still a student and became the youngest *sarpanch* of India.

She undertook developmental functions like installing "CCTV cameras for women's security, setting up water coolers, and solar panels, got a panchayat building, a library, and a sewage system" in her village. For her efforts, she was also praised by "Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi and Haryana's then CM Mr. Manohar Lal Khattar" (Yadav, 2020).

Neelam, the *sarpanch* of Chappar village, transformed the mindset of her village towards girl child, ended the practice of *ghoonights*, and promoted women

education (Pareek, 2014). *Sushma Bhadu* became the sarpanch of Dhani Miyan Khan of Haryana in 2010. She fought against the tradition of *ghoonghts*, trained women, and worked for child education. Her leadership qualities ensured numerous awards for her village for maintaining “sanitary conditions, zero dropout rate, and the best sex ratio among all villages in Haryana” (Pal, 2017).

Challenges faced by women in Haryana

Is the mere increase in women’s participation through quota sufficient to empower women in a real sense? Many field studies have been conducted in Haryana with this apprehension and questions in mind. The studies, while highlighting the fact that gender quota has increased women’s participation in Gram Panchayats, have also revealed serious socio-cultural, economic, political, and other institutional hindrances still faced by women due to which actual empowerment of women in Haryana has not yet been achieved. Let us analyse these studies in terms of the types of challenges faced by women in Haryana.

Challenge of limited Autonomy & Proxy Leadership

Sharma & Annu in their study of four districts of Haryana viz. Sonapat, Panipat, Karnal, and Rohtak revealed problems like domination of male members in the Panchayats, widespread corruption with the complicity of male members of the Panchayats and local bureaucrats, disregard for women elected representatives by male members of Panchayats and other officials, and general perception among villagers that women

representatives are incapable of being local leaders. Many women representatives were even coerced to resign through “no-confidence motions”, while many others faced tremendous pressure from political parties seeking to manipulate gender quotas for their vested interests (Sharma & Annu, 2018).

Another study conducted in Karnal district found excessive involvement of their male members as *sarpanch pati* or *sarpanch pratiniddhi*. Women *sarpanches* had poor knowledge about government departments dealing with Panchayats, had no or limited interaction with officials at the local level like *Patwaris*, *School Heads*, *JE*, *Panchayat Sachivs*, etc. and hence dealing with them was handled by their male representatives (Mayal). Dr. Kamlesh Mahajan interviewed 279 elected representatives and 30 office bearers in Haryana and concluded that 83% of women representatives still faced problems, 56% of them did not attend Panchayat meetings personally which were attended by male members of their families, 75% of women leader’s decision were taken by male members, 84% of women leaders accepted male domination as biggest hindrance (Mahajan, 2021).

Challenge of Lack of Awareness & Training

A study of Karnal district found women *sarpanches* did not have any prior training or received inadequate training and hence lacked in experience and capabilities, majority of them were pushed into elections by their families (male members especially) to take advantage of reservation (Mayal).

Another study conducted by Suman Bhambu in village Kagdana in district Sirsa

of Haryana found that almost 50% of women had extremely low awareness about the various aspects related to the Panchayati Raj system which was attributed to poor education and other social and economic issues, like low income was directly correlated with low awareness, more dissemination of information on PRIs in nuclear families as compared to joint families, etc (Bhambu, 2022). Vikas Nandal in his study in village Anwali of District Sonipat also found poor awareness among women respondents on various issues like the 73rd amendment, functions and powers of panchayats, reservation of seats, and their decision to vote was also decided by their husbands and family (Nandal, 2013). Goswami's study in five districts of Haryana - Faridabad, Mahendergarh, Nuh, Sonapat, and Yamunanagar after the 2016 Panchayati raj elections in Haryana found the restricted role of elected women representatives due to their lack of awareness about the functions of Gram Panchayats despite being educated. They suffered from lack of confidence and agency, could not articulate and comprehend local issues properly, and remained dependent on male relatives (Goswami, 2017).

Challenge of restrictive Laws & Structural Barriers

Even the policy decisions have worked against women's participation at grassroots levels. Prem Choudhry revealed that Haryana Panchayati Raj (Second Amendment) Act, 2020 even though raised seats for women in local government to 50% has hampered the entry of many women into Gram Panchayats by imposing conditions like "eighth/tenth pass, two-

child norms, toilets", etc. for contesting elections (Chowdhry, 2025). Similarly, various disqualifications like "failure to repay loans, failure to pay electricity bill arrears, not having a functional toilet at home" and educational qualifications to contest elections imposed under the "Haryana Panchayati Raj (Amendment) Act, 2015" have further worked against women. It has debarred 49% of rural women who are illiterate and excluded 69% of SC women of Haryana from contesting elections. Disqualifications will eventually exclude poor and marginalised sections, especially women from political power and decision-making opportunities and have given rise to the practice of polygamy as male members are remarrying educated females just to retain political power (Phukan, 2018).

Challenge of Patriarchal Culture & Resistance

Prem Choudhary found that elected lot of women, especially SC and BC women, still face a lot of discrimination from officials and other male representatives who prefer to interact with male members, women are discouraged from speaking in public meetings in front of males and are required to cover their faces with veils. Women are allowed to contest local elections just to retain political power at the local level and women representatives struggle to create a balance between their domestic and official responsibilities, hesitate to make independent financial decisions, and are avoided and not supported by panchayats functionaries. She concluded that women empowerment in Haryana remains symbolic as Haryanvi society is deeply ingrained in a culture that is not

mindful of its women (Chowdhry, 2025). Dahiya and Thakur’s study in six villages of Jind district revealed that due to patriarchal mindset and gender insensitive policies, the majority of women *sarpanches* reported lack of autonomy in decision making, resistance from society, lack of financial independence, lack of training, lack of dissemination of information which kept women representatives unaware. Respondents reported that the community still held a negative perception toward elected women representatives. (Dahiya & Thakur, 2025). Tripathy highlighted anti-women and undemocratic Khap structures which are bound by patriarchal and casteist mindsets restricting engagement of women in the political sphere as politics is believed to be the domain of men. Khap Panchayats practice “Politics of Exclusion” whereby women are systematically excluded from political space (Tripathi, 2017). Another study conducted in 2004 in Haryana highlighted purdah (veil) system, self-apprehension,

self-doubt, low education, poor awareness about Panchayati Raj, and lack of physical mobility as the major hindrances for women members (Kumar & Ghosh, 2024).

Challenge of Political Bias & Safety Concerns

The limited representation of women in politics has many reasons like preference for male candidates by political parties, poor political will to rectify gender imbalance in politics, and other hurdles like harassment, violence, and threats faced by women in politics. Here also, the root cause is the patriarchal mindset and cultural ethos where women are considered inferior to males and are required to follow traditional gender roles and are not considered to have capabilities of a leader, have less winnability and hence tickets are given more to male candidates. Women in politics have less access to resources and get poor support from parties which reflects the male-dominant nature of polity in Haryana (Sangita & Sharma, 2024).

Table 4 - Summary of various socio - cultural, economic, political, institutional, and personal challenges.

Factors	Challenges
Social and Cultural Factors	Gender-based disparity in participation Influence of joint family systems Caste-based exclusion (especially SC women) Purdah system and restrictions on mobility Patriarchal community attitudes Disinterest in female leadership- Gender bias in society Patriarchy dictating women’s roles Veiling norms restricting speech in public Role of khap panchayats as anti-women institutions Societal norms discouraging women’s empowerment Proxy leadership by husbands and male relatives (“Sarpanch Pati” system)

Factors	Challenges
Economic Factors	Financial dependence on men Women unable to make financial decisions Poverty and low-income correlate with low awareness and political disengagement Disqualification due to loan defaults, unpaid bills, lack of toilets (2015 Act), especially poor women Limited access to campaign resources and financial backing
Political	Dominance of male members in PRIs and families Political parties exploiting gender quotas Symbolic presence, actual power with men (Sarpanch-pati/pratinidhi phenomenon) Lack of political confidence and articulation in women Proxy participation forced by family Political parties prefer male candidates; women seen as less winnable Harassment, threats, and societal discouragement
Institutional/Legal/Policy	Lack of training or limited training No/poor interaction with officials Poor knowledge of govt schemes, processes Poor awareness of Panchayati Raj functions and responsibilities Exclusionary provisions in 2015 & 2020 Amendment Acts- Mandatory educational qualifications- Toilet, loan repayment, electricity bill requirements Non-cooperation from panchayat functionaries Lack of gender-sensitive policies and support infrastructure Dependency on males due to structural loopholes
Personal/Individual	Dual burden of domestic and official responsibilities Lack of self-confidence and communication skills Fear and hesitation in official work- Forced candidacy Discomfort in engaging with male officials

Thus, mere presence of women in Panchayats does not mean they have been empowered. They still suffered from many handicaps as revealed by so many studies. The biggest cause for superficial empowerment of women in general and especially as elected representative in Gram Panchayats is due to patriarchal, and casteist ethos which

are giving rise to all kinds of other problems and hindrances for the women at grass root levels in Haryana. Therefore, it will not be an exaggeration to conclude that empowerment of women through gender quota provided by Haryana Panchayati Raj Act, in majority of case, is just a sham and eyewash. A lot is still required to be done

to eradicate deep-rooted gender bias in the society.

SUGGESTIONS

There is need to introduce corrective mechanisms. A coordinated and integrated strategy which includes all the stakeholders is fundamental requirement. Strategy has to be implemented both at cognitive and technical levels. There is need of massive value transformation in Indian society wherein the traditional patriarchal mind-set is replaced by more egalitarian and rational value system. People, including women need to be gender sensitised. The overall literacy status, particularly female literacy status has to be improved. The entire Education system needs an overhauling. Education must ensure that new democratic, secular and rational values are imparted to students. Besides, other reforms that need to be undertaken include free and fair Panchayati elections, generation of political awareness among rural women, recognition of contribution of women representatives and special incentives for them and broadcasting the same.

SOME SUGGESTIONS THAT CAN BE IMPLEMENTED URGENTLY

1. The state government and administration have to stop the practice of male members of women representatives acting as their 'proxies'.
2. Cutting down the intervention of political parties in the functioning of panchayats, elections should be conducted fairly.
3. Women representatives must get assistance from groups of educated

women with rich experience and knowledge of local governance.

4. Capacity-building programmes for women representatives must be undertaken. They must be educated and trained in all relevant spheres like laws, rules and regulations, accounts, audits, roles and functions of Panchayats, etc. Special focus needs to be given to women from marginalized sections.
5. Women representatives must have exposure through participation in various seminars, conferences, etc. Women leaders must be digitally educated since Panchayat work is progressively getting digitized and more and more mobile phone apps are being developed for service delivery at Panchayat level. NGOs may be utilized for the capacity generation of elected women representatives.
6. More women *Gram Sachivs* should be appointed and posted in panchayats having women sarpanch to provide a comfortable working environment (Singh & Pal, 2016)
7. Efforts are required to build the self-esteem among women representatives, especially women *sarpanches* from SC/ST/OBC and Muslim communities.

CONCLUSION

Introducing women in politics at grassroots levels through gender quotas was a farsighted and revolutionary step. Experiences from the performance of Gram Panchayats from all over India including Haryana have manifested the positive impact of gender quotas for women, especially from SC/BC/ST

categories. It has transformed women's perception of themselves. They have gained self and social respect, have been able to exercise leadership capabilities, and have participated in developmental decision and policy making bringing about qualitative and inclusive changes in the lives of rural masses. However, just presence of women in Panchayats does not lead to their empowerment. They still face obstacles in achieving political empowerment through reservation in local bodies. Indian society is still dominantly a patriarchal society. Patriarchal values cut across all the sections, regions, and religions of the society. Women and EWRs both face staunch resistance from both men and women alike because patriarchy has been internalised by both sexes. The situation is worse for SC and ST women. Instances of violence, sexual abuse, and intimidation are still rampant to prevent women from entering into local politics. Illiteracy, lack of knowledge and awareness, lack of self-confidence, and casteist mindsets make the situation worse. Besides social constraints, many institutional constraints are also being used to keep women out of local politics. Thus, corrective mechanisms are urgently required. Mere gender quotas will not lead to women's political empowerment. There is an urgent need to bring value transformation in Haryana's society whereby the traditional, patriarchal, and primordial cultural ethos are replaced by modern, democratic, secular, and egalitarian values. Till the time retrograde values predominate social life, women *sarpanches/panches* in particular, and women, in general, have little chance for their emancipation and empowerment. It will take time as value transformation is

a gradual process. On a positive note, Indian society is definitely changing and eventually, we will witness holistic and realistic empowerment of women in the coming future.

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